

Teachers' motivational profiles and their longitudinal associations with teaching quality

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ABSTRACT

This study used an integrated theoretical approach to investigate teacher motivation and its influence on teaching quality. Drawing on Expectancy-Value-Theory and Achievement-Goal-Theory, a person-centered approach was used to investigate how multiple characteristics (i.e., self-efficacy, enthusiasm, and goal orientation) combined to form teachers' motivational profiles. The profiles were then analyzed to see if there was a link to teaching quality. Latent profile analysis for 156 secondary-level mathematics teachers identified three motivational profiles which differed only in their performance goals: low performance goal-oriented (49%), high performance goal-oriented (38%), and high performance-avoidance goal-oriented (13%). Multilevel path analysis showed that motivational profile membership was not significantly related to student-rated teaching quality when baseline teaching quality was controlled ($N = 1497$ available on both measurement points). The findings revealed that the link between teacher motivation and teaching quality was less clear than expected. Possible reasons for the results are discussed.

1. Introduction

Teacher motivation is considered a core element of teacher professionalism and is therefore of great importance for teaching. However, the few existing longitudinal studies do not consistently support this assumption. A possible explanation for the inconclusive results is the way teacher motivation is conceptualized: Although conceptualized as multidimensional, the vast majority of empirical research on teacher motivation has followed a variable-centered approach, where the effects of single motivational characteristics on teaching quality (mostly: self-efficacy, achievement goals, and enthusiasm, see Kunter, 2014) were usually examined separately (e.g., Burić & Kim, 2020; Butler & Shibaz, 2008; Kunter et al., 2008). Thus, little is known about the combination and configuration of motivational characteristics and its impact on teachers' behavior.

It seems important to examine the interplay of multiple motivational characteristics to capture the holistic phenomenon of teacher motivation adequately, since individual characteristics from single theoretical traditions only tap specific aspects and processes of motivation (Kaplan, 2014). Researchers therefore have repeatedly called for an integrative approach, emphasizing that such an approach would also allow the identification of conceptual overlaps across different motivational

theories and the development of a more nuanced understanding of the phenomenon of motivation (e.g., Anderman, 2020; Linnenbrink-Garcia & Wormington, 2019; Neves de Jesus & Lens, 2005). This seems particularly promising, since motivational characteristics do not operate independently from each other but might act in a multiplicative way (Wigfield & Eccles, 2000). It might be that a combination of multiple characteristics has an effect on teacher behavior rather than each of them acting separately. It is therefore crucial to examine the combination of pivotal motivational characteristics simultaneously.

To address these issues, this study adopts a person-centered approach and provides an integrative perspective on teacher motivation, drawing simultaneously on characteristics of both Expectancy-Value-Theory (EVT; i.e., enthusiasm, self-efficacy) and Achievement-Goal-Theory (AGT; i.e., goal orientations). Whereas variable-centered analyses depend on rigorous a priori theoretical assumptions regarding the interaction of the characteristics, person-centered approaches such as latent profile analysis allow the exploration of possible configurations of numerous characteristics and their collective effect on teaching quality. This is especially accommodating when a large number of variables are examined simultaneously and little is known about their interplay.

In the subsequent sections, we outline the conceptualization of

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teacher motivation. We then demonstrate why the person-centered approach is suitable for investigating teachers' motivational profiles and their longitudinal relation with teaching quality. We also review how other studies have investigated motivational profiles with the characteristics examined in the present study. Finally, we present the conceptualization of teaching quality and empirical relations between teacher motivation and teaching quality in variable-centered studies.

1.1. Teacher motivation: an integrative perspective

Motivation is commonly understood to be a personal characteristic, an inner activating force that determines people's actions (Graham & Weiner, 1996). Modern motivation research however is based on a more differentiated and multidimensional understanding. Motivation is viewed as a combination of internal characteristics and processes that explain the diverse underlying reasons for people's actions (Pintrich, 2003). This multidimensional understanding of motivation has been increasingly applied to research on teachers. In recent decades, several researchers have studied the complex field of teacher motivation applying different motivational theories for the teaching profession (Richardson et al., 2014). A large body of literature has focused on characteristics associated with EVT (Eccles, 1983) and AGT (Ames, 1992; Dweck, 1986) to describe teachers' motivation in their teaching context (Kaplan, 2014). Teachers' self-efficacy (as an expectancy component) and teachers' enthusiasm (as a value component) are among the most commonly examined motivational characteristics that relate to the core assumptions of EVT (Kunter & Holzberger, 2014; Wigfield & Eccles, 2000). *Teachers' self-efficacy* refers to the belief in their ability to influence student engagement and learning, even in times of difficulty (Klassen & Chiu, 2010). *Teachers' enthusiasm*, as an intrinsic orientation, is defined as the "degree of enjoyment, excitement, and pleasure that teachers typically experience in their professional activities" (Kunter et al., 2008, p. 470). The extent to which a teacher enjoys teaching is regarded as activity-related enthusiasm, called enthusiasm for teaching.

With reference to AGT, *teachers' goal orientations* are conceptualized as relatively stable orientations that influence personal definitions and interpretations of success and so explain why and how teachers behave in achievement-related situations (Butler, 2007). Commonly distinguished achievement goals of teachers are: (1) learning goals (aiming to improve their competencies), (2) performance-approach goals (aiming to demonstrate their competencies), (3) performance-avoidance goals (aiming to avoid demonstrating competence deficits), and (4) work-avoidance goals (aiming to minimize work effort as much as possible).

Teachers' self-efficacy, enthusiasm, and the four goal orientations listed above have primarily either been examined in separate studies or in studies where only their unique effects were considered in a variable-centered approach and any interplay was ignored (e.g., Holzberger et al., 2013; Kunter et al., 2008; Lazarides et al., 2021; Retelsdorf et al., 2010).

Concerns have been raised about the practice of investigating single motivational characteristics at once, for several reasons.

First, different motivational characteristics and their underlying theoretical backgrounds refer to different aspects and processes of motivation and therefore do not adequately capture the complex and holistic phenomenon of teacher motivation when examined separately (Kaplan, 2014).

Second, although EVT and AGT are considered to be two distinct motivational theories, there is a degree of overlap between them (see e.g., Anderman, 2020; Hulleman et al., 2008; Linnenbrink-Garcia & Wormington, 2019). Both theories share common core assumptions with Social-Cognitive-Theory (Bandura, 2006), including the concepts of reciprocal determinism and agency (see Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018). Integrating EVT and AGT seems particularly promising since both theories collectively measure aspects of the two essential

motivational questions outlined in the often-cited framework by Wigfield et al. (2006)¹: "Can I do this task?" (competence-related beliefs) and "Do I want to do this task and why?" (value-related beliefs) (p. 934). Whereas teachers' self-efficacy represents a typical competence belief, teachers' enthusiasm and goal orientations represent value related components. Previous variable-centered studies on teacher motivation support the assumption that characteristics from EVT and AGT are interrelated and so should not be treated independently (e.g., Neves de Jesus & Lens, 2005; Schiefele & Schaffner, 2015).

Third, a simultaneous investigation of multiple characteristics is also prompted by both theoretical frameworks. According to EVT, the motivation for a specific behavior stems from the multiplicative product of the subjective expectation of the results of action (expectancy component) and the subjective value attached to it (value component). Since these components may or may not concur, several patterns of combinations may exist. For example, some teachers may have high competence beliefs and perceive teaching as highly relevant and satisfying, while others share the high importance value but feel less competent, or vice versa. The multiplicative link implies that motivation will be especially high when a teacher scores highly on both components. But it could also be that the two components can somewhat compensate for another (Trautwein et al., 2012). Researchers also argue that in AGT, the interactive effect of a combination of different goals, such as learning and performance-approach goals (as in the "multiple-goal perspective"), explains more of the variance in outcomes than do the additive effects (see e.g., Harackiewicz et al., 2002).

Fourth, previous studies on student motivation have shown that characteristics from EVT and AGT jointly predict achievement-related performance, underscoring the need to integrate the two theories in future studies (Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018; Plante et al., 2013).

Finally, adopting an integrative motivational perspective also has practical advantages. Studying the key motivational characteristics of EVT and AGT simultaneously allows for a more complete picture of the motivation that teachers experience in their professional life, which in turn is likely to be more useful to teachers when introduced in professional development courses. It would also be possible to examine whether only teachers who are deemed to have high levels for all characteristics can provide high quality teaching, or whether certain characteristics could compensate for others. Specific motivational profile configurations may (or may not) significantly influence teaching practices. These profiles might suggest whether motivational characteristics should be fostered in general or, in the case of compensatory effects, whether promoting certain motivational characteristics is sufficient. Given that the findings of single-theory studies are limited in their range of applications (Linnenbrink-Garcia & Wormington, 2019), an integrative approach to teacher motivation and its influence on teaching outcomes has the potential to enable the development of more suitable prevention and intervention strategies for teachers with different profile configurations.

Summing up, teacher motivation represents a complex and dynamic system, which should not be reduced to single motivational characteristics and their associated theories (Kaplan, 2014). Drawing on EVT and AGT simultaneously, we aim to provide a more comprehensive picture of teacher motivation. Compared to student motivation, little is yet known about the interplay of these two prominent theories within the context of teacher motivation, providing a strong argument for an integrative person-centered approach.

¹ The framework also includes "What do I have to do to succeed?", which is grounded in literature regarding achievement regulation, and thus goes beyond the scope of teachers' motivational beliefs.

1.2. Merits of the person-centered approach

Two different empirical methods have been repeatedly found to be useful for examining the combination of multiple characteristics: variable-centered approaches (e.g., multiple regressions) or person-centered approaches (e.g., LPA). The variable-centered approach commonly used in motivational research examines the unique association of two or more independent motivational variables with academic outcomes in a given population by using statistical multiplicative interaction terms. Since regression modeling requires prior information about the type, number, and order of possible interactions, it is particularly suitable for theory-based, deductive investigations (Bauer & Shanahan, 2007). A limitation of this approach is that the analyses become more complex as the number of variables and their possible interactions increases, which also affects interpretation. For example, for the six motivational characteristics in the present study, six main effects, fifteen two-way interactions, twenty three-way interactions, fifteen four-way interactions, six five-way interactions, and one six-way interaction could be considered (Elliot & McGregor, 2001).

In contrast, a person-centered approach, in which many interaction effects are analyzed simultaneously, is more suitable in contexts where there are a large number of motivational characteristics (Morin & Marsh, 2015). For example, using LPA it is possible to identify naturally occurring subgroups of teachers who have multiple different motivational characteristics. This gives insight into the combination of multiple motivational characteristics on the individual level, instead of the whole sample characteristics described by variable-centered analyses. Accounting for the intraindividual heterogeneity within a sample is important, as teachers have multiple reasons for engaging in their teaching (Kaplan, 2014). A person-centered approach, unlike a variable-centered approach, identifies distinct configurations (e.g., motivational profiles) and their prevalence and thus allows for a better understanding of the interplay of multiple motivational characteristics (see e.g., Watt et al., 2021). For example, whereas performance-approach and performance-avoidance goals are closely related in variable-centered studies (Nitsche et al., 2011), the few person-centered analyses indicate that this is not the case for all teachers. Kunst et al. (2018), for example, identified a subgroup of teachers, characterized by low performance-approach but high performance-avoidance goals. This also highlights that statistical problems such as multicollinearity of both performance goals are less likely in person-centered studies than in multiple regressions (Wormington & Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2017).

Finally, and most importantly, person-centered analyses are not as dependent on theoretically founded relations between predictor and outcome as in variable-centered analyses (Howard & Hoffman, 2017), which makes them more suitable for an exploratory inductive approach like the present study, where the interplay of multiple characteristics and their relation to educational outcomes has not yet been clarified for teachers (Kaplan, 2014).

1.3. Motivational profiles of teachers

None of the few person-centered studies that investigate the key teacher motivational characteristics of enthusiasm, self-efficacy, and goal orientation, investigate multiple motivational characteristics. They measure subscales or sub-dimensions of one of these motivational characteristics to identify profiles. Keller et al. (2018) investigated teachers' enthusiasm and identified four profiles (high, externalized, internalized, and low enthusiasm), whose high enthusiasm profile was the most predictive for students' emotions. Rodríguez et al. (2014) found three profiles of teacher self-efficacy (high, medium, and low self-efficacy), where a medium self-efficacy profile was the most predictive for students' affective-motivational beliefs. These findings confirm that although mainly level differences were found, intraindividual configurations might also be of relevance. Two recent studies

investigated teachers' goal orientations and identified complex configurations of profile level and shape: diffuse, moderate learning, high avoidance, performance-oriented, and success-oriented (Kunst et al., 2018); average all goals, mastery high, mastery/performance low, high all, mastery/performance high, and work avoidance high (Daumiller, Janke, Butler, Dickhäuser, & Dresel, 2020). In line with the multiple-goal perspective, both studies conclude that the "high learning and performance approach goal profile" is the most beneficial for professional development and self-concept.

Yet, there are no integrative person-centered studies of teachers' motivational profiles that simultaneously examine the interplay of characteristics of both EVT and AGT, although such an approach could result in a more comprehensive overview of the holistic phenomenon of teacher motivation. Indeed, two studies on student motivation that follow a similar approach highlight the added value of integrating multiple characteristics related to EVT and AGT (Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018). Similar profile configurations such as quantitatively different (high, moderate, low) and divergent profiles (e.g., intrinsic and confident profile characterized by high competence, task value, and learning goals, but low levels of performance goals) were found in both studies. Interestingly, students assigned to the high profile (high all) showed equal engagement and achievement as students assigned to the intrinsic and confident profile. Most importantly, both studies provided first evidence that integrating multiple characteristics associated with both theories in a person-centered approach explains more variance in the profile variables, shows higher probabilities of accurate profile classification and accounts for more variance in outcome variables than when only characteristics associated with one theory (achievement goals) are included.

Encouraged by these findings, the aim of the current study is to investigate, for the first time, an integrative model of teacher motivation based on EVT and AGT using a person-centered approach. To test the usefulness of teachers' motivational profiles, we also examine whether these profiles relate to teaching quality. We selected this outcome variable since a commonly investigated topic in teacher motivation research is the extent to which individual differences in motivational constructs influence teaching quality in the classroom (Kunter & Holzberger, 2014).

1.4. Teacher motivation and teaching quality

In research on educational effectiveness, teaching quality is considered a crucial determinant of student achievement (Hattie, 2009). Teaching quality is regarded a co-constructive and context-specific process, which is influenced by the interactions of teachers, their students, and the learning content (e.g., Bell et al., 2012; Klieme et al., 2009; Praetorius et al., 2018).

In German-speaking countries a well-established and frequently used model to conceptualize teaching quality is the Three Basic Dimensions (TBD) model which comprises the following dimensions (see Klieme et al., 2009): *Classroom management* focuses on maximizing time on task by preventing and dealing effectively with disruptions and disciplinary conflicts during teaching. *Cognitive activation* aims to foster students' higher-order thinking by, for example, using complex problem-solving tasks. *Student support* aims to promote the quality of social interactions and to address students' basic needs and interests, by, for example, using constructive teacher feedback and a positive approach toward students' errors. Most studies on the three basic dimensions have used either observer or student ratings of teaching quality as teacher judgments are usually seen as less reliable (in terms of inter-rater reliability) and valid than observer or student judgments (Clausen, 2002; Praetorius et al., 2018).

The relations between the three basic dimensions and teacher motivation have so far only been examined in variable-centered studies. Studies on enthusiasm have found positive cross-sectional relations with student-rated and teacher-rated dimensions of teaching quality

(classroom management, cognitive activation, and student support) (e.g., Holzberger et al., 2016; Kunter et al., 2008). The results of the few longitudinal studies are rather inconsistent and vary depending on the specific dimension of teaching quality being studied. Whereas positive effects of teachers' enthusiasm were found for teacher-rated classroom management (Bleck, 2019) and change in student-rated classroom management (Lazarides et al., 2021), no significant effects were found for changes in student-perceived emotional support and instructional clarity (Lazarides et al., 2021). For teachers' self-efficacy, positive cross-sectional links with all student- and teacher-rated basic dimensions have been identified in multiple studies (e.g., Burić & Kim, 2020; Fauth et al., 2019; Holzberger et al., 2013). However, like the results for enthusiasm, the findings of the few longitudinal studies are mixed, and the relations differ depending on who is rating teaching quality: Whereas Künsting et al. (2016) found longitudinal effects of teachers' self-efficacy on teacher-rated teaching quality (all three dimensions), no longitudinal effects of teachers' self-efficacy were found on student-rated teaching quality (Holzberger et al., 2013; Lazarides et al., 2021).

There has been less research on associations between teachers' goal orientations and teaching quality. A positive correlation was found between learning goals and student perception of teacher support (Butler & Shiba, 2008). Similarly, Retelsdorf et al. (2010) reported a positive link between learning goals and teacher-rated cognitive activation. However, no significant associations with cognitive activation were found for performance goals and work-avoidance goals. Longitudinally, learning goals were found to have a positive effect and work-avoidance goals had a negative effect on teacher-rated cognitive activation (Retelsdorf et al., 2010).

Overall, the studies reviewed do not provide a firm indication of whether key motivational characteristics are associated with teaching quality. Whereas findings from cross-sectional studies seem to be more consistent, longitudinal relations are less clear than expected. However, as teaching quality is considered variable across time, at least to some extent (e.g., Gaertner & Brunner, 2018; Lazarides et al., 2021; Praetorius et al., 2014), it is important to derive a clear picture of longitudinal relations.

Because studies examining the relation between motivational characteristics and teaching quality have used a variable-centered approach, the characteristics have been examined in isolation and any interplay between characteristics has been neglected. To close this research gap, the present study aims to examine motivational characteristics simultaneously in a person-centered approach to develop a more comprehensive understanding of teacher motivation. This holistic approach should in turn shed light on the inconsistent findings regarding the longitudinal relation between teaching motivation and teaching quality. Finally, a clearer picture of the longitudinal relations between teacher motivation and teaching quality would facilitate the transfer of empirical findings into practice.

1.5. The present study

The present study aimed to investigate teacher motivation and its effects on teaching quality from an integrated theoretical perspective similar to that used in recent studies on student motivation (Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018). Drawing on EVT and AGT, we examined which, and what combination, of the most commonly researched motivational characteristics are found in teachers. Since the four types of goals are conceptually different (see Butler & Shiba, 2008) and associated with teaching differently, we decided to include self-efficacy, enthusiasm, and all four types of goals in the present study. The first research question, therefore, asked what motivational profiles relating to teachers' enthusiasm for teaching, self-efficacy, and the four different goal orientations could be identified. As this is the first study known to the authors with this specific research question, we follow an exploratory approach.

On the basis of fairly similar investigations that focused on students' motivational profiles (Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018), one could cautiously hypothesize that three to six motivational profiles characterized by level differences (high, medium, low) would be found, where a high motivational profile indicates high levels on all indicators except for performance-avoidance and work-avoidance goals (and vice versa for the low profile).² These studies also led us to expect that we would find divergent patterns of motivational characteristics.

Having identified teachers' motivational profiles, the present study aimed to examine whether and if so to what extent different profiles have an effect on changes in teaching quality. On the basis of previous studies on teachers' motivational profiles (see section 1.3), we expected that the high motivation profile would have the strongest effect on changes in teaching quality compared to other profiles. However, based on the findings of Linnenbrink-Garcia et al. (2018) on student motivation, we expected that there would be more than one combination of motivational beliefs with a positive relation to teaching quality.

2. Method

2.1. Participants and procedure

We used data from a longitudinal study on mathematics in German secondary schools ("Gymnasien"). This dataset had already been used for examining other research questions about the relations between teacher motivation and teaching practices (Dresel et al., 2013; Praetorius et al., 2017). From the total of $N = 165$ teachers, 9 had to be excluded due to missing values on all variables of interest or due to irregularities in the data distribution. Thus, the sample comprised 156 mathematics teachers (58% female, average age of 41.2 years, $SD = 12.50$, average teaching experience of 13.0 years, $SD = 12.28$). At Time 1, teachers filled out a questionnaire on their motivation and their 3910 students (50% female, average age of 10.2 years, $SD = 0.50$) filled out a questionnaire on their perception of teaching quality. Both questionnaires were in German.

One year later, entire classrooms who were still taught by the same teacher were included in the analyses and once again answered the same questionnaire about their perception of teaching quality. As only same teacher-student combinations participated at Time 2, this resulted in a reduction in data, with 1497 student ratings being available at Time 2. The dropout of 88 teachers and their classes did not influence the analyses, however. Missing value analyses indicated no significant differences between classes that participated at both times and classes that participated only once (see Table 1). The descriptive mean differences were also small on all scales (Cohen's $d \leq 0.11$). Thus, missing data was considered missing at random, allowing the use of full information maximum likelihood (FIML).

2.2. Measures

At Time 1, teacher motivation was assessed by self-ratings of enthusiasm, self-efficacy, and goal orientations with scales that have consistently shown good psychometric properties and have been used in a number of studies (e.g., Kunter et al., 2011; Nitsche et al., 2011; Schmitz & Schwarzer, 2000). At Times 1 and 2, students filled out a questionnaire on their perception of their mathematics teacher's teaching quality, including items measuring classroom management, cognitive activation, and student support. The measures have shown good reliability on the class level across various samples (e.g., Kunter & Baumert, 2006). To account for the level specific reliability, we estimated McDonald's omega (ω), which is regarded as preferable to

² However, transferring findings from student motivation to teacher motivation has to be done cautiously, as motivation is not experienced the same way for both populations (Kaplan, 2014).

Table 1
Relations between teacher motivational characteristics and teaching quality dimensions.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)	(11)	(12)
<i>Time 1</i>												
(1) Enthusiasm for teaching	4.20 (0.58)											
(2) Self-efficacy	.28**	2.93 (0.32)										
(3) Learning goal orientation	.27**	.32**	4.18 (0.45)									
(4) Performance-approach goal orientation	-.01	.08	.18*	2.08 (0.80)								
(5) Performance-avoidance goal orientation	-.11	-.05	.14	.73**	2.45 (0.83)							
(6) Work-avoidance goal orientation	.06	-.01	.01	.15	.09	1.99 (0.82)						
(7) Classroom management ICC(1) = 0.22, ICC(2) = 0.88	.35**	.00	-.03	-.11	-.15	.04	3.90 (0.58)					
(8) Cognitive activation ICC(1) = 0.03, ICC(2) = 0.44	.15	.06	.10	.03	-.03	.19*	.10	3.45 (0.17)				
(9) Student support ICC(1) = 0.11, ICC(2) = 0.76	.22**	.20*	.12	.02	-.01	.07	.19*	.38**	4.11 (0.40)			
<i>Time 2</i>												
(10) Classroom management ICC(1) = 0.27, ICC(2) = 0.89	.27*	.12	-.04	-.16	-.19	.18	.68**	.22	.12	3.67 (0.69)		
(11) Cognitive activation ICC(1) = 0.12, ICC(2) = 0.75	-.03	-.03	-.03	-.04	.02	.09	.36**	.28*	.19	.49**	3.36 (0.28)	
(12) Student support ICC(1) = 0.19, ICC(2) = 0.84	.22	.09	.03	-.19	-.13	.09	.38**	.17	.44**	.43**	.68**	3.80 (0.57)
(13) Data completeness	.09	-.05	.04	-.04	-.07	.06	.13	-.06	.00	-.01	-.07	-.01

Note. Mean values and standard deviations of the variables are presented on the diagonal. Measurement interval between Time 1 and Time 2 was 12 months. Data completeness coded 0 = incomplete; 1 = complete. $N_{T1} = 156$ teachers with 3910 students; $n_{T2} = 68$ teachers with 1497 students. * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$.

single-level estimates such as Cronbach’s alpha (Geldhof et al., 2014).

2.2.1. Teacher motivation

Teachers’ enthusiasm for teaching was assessed with a two-item scale from the German COACTIV study (Kunter et al., 2011). The two items were: “I teach mathematics in this class with great enthusiasm” and “I really enjoy teaching mathematics in this class,” rated on a 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree). Cronbach’s α for this scale was .74.

Teachers’ self-efficacy was assessed using a 10-item scale from Schwarzer and Schmitz (1999), including items such as: “I am confident that I can develop creative ideas for changing unfavorable instructional structures,” rated on a 4-point scale (1 = disagree, 4 = agree). Cronbach’s α for this scale was .73.

Teachers’ goal-orientations were assessed using a questionnaire by Nitsche et al. (2011), comprising four types of goals with statements starting with “In my vocation, I aspire ...,” rated on a 5-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree): nine learning goal items (e.g., “... to improve my pedagogical knowledge and competence”; Cronbach’s $\alpha = .73$), 12 performance-approach goal items (e.g., “... my students to realize that I teach better than other teachers”; Cronbach’s $\alpha = .91$), 12 performance-avoidance goal items (e.g., “... to not show my students when I have more trouble to meet the job demands than other teachers”; Cronbach’s $\alpha = .88$), and three work-avoidance goal items (e.g., “... to get through the day with little effort”; Cronbach’s $\alpha = .74$).

2.2.2. Teaching quality

Classroom management was assessed by the aspect of time on task with a 3-item scale from PISA 2003 (Ramm et al., 2006). A sample item is: “In mathematics, it takes a long time at the start of the lesson until the students settle down and start working,” rated on a 6-point scale (1 =

strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree). Within-level ω was .77 at Time 1 and .82 at Time 2, whereas between-level ω was .92 at Time 1 and .93 at Time 2.

Cognitive activation was assessed by the aspect of challenging tasks and questions, with a 5-item scale, also from PISA 2003 (Ramm et al., 2006). A sample item is: “In mathematics, our teacher asks questions that cannot be answered directly but stimulate thinking about them,” rated on a 5-point scale (1 = never, 5 = always). Within-level ω was .77 at Time 1 and .84 at Time 2, whereas between-level ω was .82 at Time 1 and .93 at Time 2.

Student support was measured as the aspect of emotional student support, which is expressed through the experience of social relatedness. This dimension was assessed with a 5-item scale developed by Wild (1999). A sample item is: “In mathematics, I feel accepted and supported by my teacher”, rated on a 6-point scale (1 = strongly disagree, 6 = strongly agree). Within-level ω was .87 at Time 1 and .90 at Time 2, whereas between-level ω was .95 at both Time 1 and Time 2.

2.3. Statistical analyses

2.3.1. Cross-sectional latent profile analysis

To identify teachers’ motivational profiles, we conducted a cross-sectional LPA. Thereby, the best fitting subgroups for teachers with similar patterns of the six motivational characteristics were estimated. All scales were derived from the averaged item values and represented manifest variables, as the sample size did not allow latent modeling. Starting with a two-profile model, we iteratively added up to $K = 7$. To determine the best fitting solution, we considered multiple fit criteria outlined by Nylund et al. (2007). The Bayesian information criterion (BIC) was used to compare the relative fit of multiple models to the data while considering the complexity and the sample size of each model.

Lower BIC values indicate a better fit (Raftery, 1995). For statistical model comparison, the bootstrap likelihood ratio difference test (BLRT) was performed. A significant *p*-value indicates that the *k*-profile solution fits the data better than the *k*-1 model. Additionally, the value of entropy was determined, indicating the classification accuracy of the profile solution (McLachlan & Peel, 2005). Interpretability of the class solutions, differentiability of the individual profiles, and class sizes were also considered (Lubke & Muthén, 2005).

After identifying the best fitting solution, we performed Kruskal-Wallis tests with Bonferroni post hoc comparisons to examine whether the profiles differed on motivational characteristics. To support profile interpretation, *z*-scores of the indicators were calculated to account for the different scaling of teachers' self-efficacy (4-point Likert scale) compared to the other scales (5-point Likert scale). The profile interpretation thus refers to group comparison rather than absolute mean scores. As there are no clear criteria in the literature for which values are considered high or low, we followed an approach used in profile research for interpreting the nature of the profiles (e.g., Rouse et al., 2020). Accordingly, values of over ± 1 *SD* were considered very high/low, values of ± 0.5 to 1 *SD* as high/low, and values up to ± 0.5 *SD* as slightly above/below average.

2.3.2. Multilevel path analyses to predict changes in teaching quality

Three manifest scales were used for the teaching quality dimensions. Given the hierarchical structure of the data, the manifest scales were then decomposed into level 1 (within-class), consisting of individual student ratings and level 2 (between-class), containing students' class-wise aggregated ratings (for latent aggregation see Lüdtke et al., 2008). Teacher motivation was included on level 2. Teaching quality variables were centered at the group mean.

To investigate whether and how motivational profile membership has an effect on changes³ in student-perceived teaching quality from Time 1 to Time 2, we conducted multilevel path analyses (Bryk & Raudenbush, 1987). When using the term *effect*, we refer to statistical effects rather than causal effects, since longitudinal data without an experimental design does not allow for causal inferences (Wunsch et al., 2010). Following the methodological standard for longitudinal analyses, teaching quality at Time 1 served as control variable on both levels. Controlling for teaching quality at Time 1 is also suitable since we assumed that teaching quality might have changed during the year to some extent, as students at Time 1 had just recently entered secondary school, classes had new compositions and were taught by new teachers with relationships yet to be established. The cross-sectional relations between motivational profiles and teaching quality at Time 1 were modeled correlatively within the model. One model including all three dimensions of teaching quality was estimated, to consider their cross-sectional interrelations at both measurement points. These variables were modeled simultaneously at levels 1 and 2. Profile membership was introduced as a set of dummy variables to investigate profile differences. Mplus Version 8.0 was used for all analyses (Muthén & Muthén, 1998-2017).

3. Results

3.1. Descriptive statistics

Table 1 shows descriptive statistics for all of the variables assessed and their intercorrelations. ICC(1) for the student ratings of teaching quality ranged from .03 to .27, indicating that between 3% and 27% of

the observed variance in the variables was due to systematic between-class differences. Motivational characteristics correlated weakly to highly with each other ($r = .18$ to $.73$), confirming dependencies among them. Regarding the intercorrelations between the student-reported teaching quality dimensions, small to high correlations were found ($r = .19$ to $.68$). The test-retest correlations for teaching quality ranged from .28 to .68. The bivariate correlations between teacher motivation and teaching quality at Time 1 were small to moderate, ranging from close to zero (e.g., for learning goals) to .35 (e.g., for enthusiasm). The longitudinal correlational pattern between teacher motivation (Time 1) and teaching quality (Time 2) indicated no significant relations except for that between enthusiasm and classroom management ($r = .27$).

3.2. Identification of teachers' motivational profiles

The fit statistic BIC and the significant *p*-value in BLRT statistics indicated a three-profile solution (see Table 2). Although the corresponding *p*-value for the five-profile solution was also significant, we retained the three-profile structure, considering the principle of parsimony and the higher probability of alpha error accumulation for statistical analyses based on a five-profile solution (Morin & Marsh, 2015). The five-profile solution did not add meaningful new insight, as similar profiles emerged with profound profile differences on performance and work-avoidance goals, rather than on enthusiasm, self-efficacy, or learning goals. Finally, the interpretation of the five-profile solution proved much more complicated than the interpretation of the more parsimonious three-profile solution.⁴

In the final profile solution, the posterior probabilities that individuals belong to their assigned profiles were very high (.94 - .95), with classes being highly distinguishable from one another (see Table 3).

Table 4 reports the descriptive statistics of the different motivational profiles. Fig. 1 shows a graphical representation of the three-profile solution. When considering the standardized means of the three profiles, the largest profile differences were identified for the two performance goals (approach and avoidance). By contrast, enthusiasm, self-efficacy, learning goals, and work-avoidance goals had similar mean levels across the three profiles, with values slightly above/below average. Post hoc analyses confirmed that profile differences were only significant for performance-approach ($F(2,153) = 224.91, p \leq .001, \eta^2 = .75$) and performance-avoidance goals ($F(2,153) = 106.79, p \leq .001, \eta^2 = .58$). These profound differences in the between-profile comparison were used as a guide when naming profiles.

The largest profile had low scores for both performance-approach and performance-avoidance goals. This profile was therefore called "low performance goal oriented," (PGO). Teachers in the second profile group scored very high on performance-approach and high on performance-avoidance goals. This profile was therefore named "high

Table 2
Fit statistics for the different profile solutions.

k	BIC	BLRT	aLMR (p)	Entropy	N for each profile
2	1640.63	-734.47	-	.91	20, 136
3	1632.91	-712.93	< 0.001	.86	77, 20, 59
4	1644.79	-701.20	.06	.86	55, 25, 19, 57
5	1651.29	-686.77	.01	.87	19, 57, 35, 24, 21
6	1661.24	-674.08	.07	.92	29, 8, 30, 45, 20, 24
7	1673.50	-662.53	.09	.90	29, 5, 34, 22, 21, 27, 18

Note. The selected model is highlighted in bold. BIC = Bayesian information criterion; aLMR = adjusted Lo-Mendell-Rubin likelihood ratio test; k = number of latent profiles in the model.

³ The term *change* does not refer to a latent-change-score approach, but to a covariance analytical approach, where the outcome variable at Time 2 (here teaching quality) is predicted by the independent variable (here motivational profile membership), after partialling out pre-scores of teaching quality at Time 1. For a recent discussion on both approaches see Köhler et al. (2021).

⁴ For a graphical representation of the five-profile solution, please see Appendix.

Table 3
Posterior probabilities associated with the three-profile model.

Profile	1	2	3
1	.94	.03	.04
2	.05	.95	.00
3	.04	.01	.95

Note. Average probabilities (rows) for most likely latent profile membership (columns).

Table 4
Mean (SD) and standardized Z-scores for the six motivational characteristics of the three latent profiles.

Profile variables	Profile 1 ^a : PGO ⁻		Profile 2 ^b : PGO ⁺		Profile 3 ^c : PAGO ⁺	
	M (SD)	Z	M (SD)	Z	M (SD)	Z
Enthusiasm for teaching	4.31 (0.54)	0.13	4.05 (0.54)	-0.32	4.20 (0.63)	-0.07
Self-efficacy	2.93 (0.30)	0.00	2.90 (0.40)	-0.09	2.95 (0.32)	0.04
Learning goal orientation	4.18 (0.47)	0.00	4.07 (0.51)	-0.23	4.18 (0.41)	0.08
Performance-approach goal orientation	1.50 (0.40) ^c	-0.73	1.73 (0.47) ^c	-0.43	2.96 (0.39) ^{ab}	1.10
Performance-avoidance goal orientation	1.82 (0.60) ^{bc}	-0.76	3.30 (0.51) ^a	1.02	2.99 (0.47) ^a	0.65
Work-avoidance goal orientation	1.97 (0.81)	-0.03	1.60 (0.50)	-0.48	2.15 (0.88)	0.19

Note. ^{abc} indicates significant differences in motivational characteristics between profiles ($p < .01$).

Fig. 1. Standardized means for the motivational characteristics in the three profiles. PGO (-/+) = (low/high) performance goal oriented; PAGO⁺ = high performance-avoidance goal oriented.

performance goal oriented,” (PGO⁺). The smallest profile included teachers with a slightly below average score on performance-approach goals and a very high score on performance-avoidance goals. This profile was therefore named “high performance-avoidance goal oriented,” (PAGO⁺).

Profile membership was not significantly predicted by gender ($\chi^2(2, N = 154) = 3.74, p = .15$, Cramer’s $V = .16$), age ($F(2, 143) = .58, p = .56, \eta^2 = .008$), or teaching experience ($F(2, 150) = .23, p = .80, \eta^2 = .003$).

3.3. Relations between motivational profile membership and teaching quality

To examine the relation between teachers’ motivational profiles and teaching quality we used profile membership as dummy variables to compare the motivational profiles. Profile PGO⁻ was treated as the reference group.⁵ Fig. 2 presents the results of the multilevel path analyses.

3.3.1. Cross-sectional relations

The relations between teachers’ motivational profiles and dimensions of teaching quality at Time 1 were non-significant. There was no statistically significant difference between profiles for any of the three teaching quality dimensions.

3.3.2. Longitudinal relations

Like the cross-sectional relations, teaching quality at Time 2, when controlled for teaching quality at Time 1, was not predicted to a statistically significant degree by profile membership. Students of teachers in profiles PGO⁺ and PAGO⁺ perceived no significant differences in classroom management, cognitive activation, and student support compared to students of teachers in PGO⁻. Altogether, those variables explained the following extent of between-level variance: 56% of classroom management, 14% of cognitive activation, and 23% of student support. However, this was attributable to the baseline control of teaching quality.

4. Discussion

Based on a multidimensional understanding of teacher motivation, the purpose of this study was to shed light on teachers’ motivational

profiles. The study adopted an integrative perspective of teacher motivation, investigating multiple motivational characteristics

⁵ PGO⁻ was chosen as a reference group, as teachers in this profile mainly pursued learning goals, which has been positively related to teaching quality (e.g. Butler and Shibaz, 2008). The comparison of this profile with profile PGO⁺ and PAGO⁺ is therefore particularly interesting. In order to verify the results, the analyses were also conducted using profile PGO⁺ as a reference group, where none of the effects on the three teaching quality dimensions were significant.

Fig. 2. Multilevel path model predicting student-perceived teaching quality by profile membership. Standardized regression coefficients. All correlations among the exogenous and among the endogenous variables were freely estimated. T1 = time point 1; T2 = time point 2. $\chi^2(12) = 29.32, p \leq .001$; RMSEA = .02; CFI = .98; TLI = .94; standardized root mean squared residual (SRMR) within = .03; SRMR between = .09. * $p < .05$.

simultaneously instead of individually. The study also aimed to provide information about longitudinal relations by linking the different profiles to teaching quality, which is particularly important as the vast majority of the literature is cross-sectional and the findings of the few longitudinal studies are inconsistent.

4.1. Description and possible explanations of the motivational profiles

The three latent profiles found showed average levels of enthusiasm, self-efficacy, learning goals, and work-avoidance goals. Therefore, teachers were classed as having average motivation for these characteristics. Contrary to expectations, we did not find substantial qualitative level differences across the profiles. Interestingly, pronounced profile differences were found only for the two performance goals, insofar as teachers strived to demonstrate their competence (performance-approach goals) or to hide their incompetence (performance-avoidance goals). Half of the teachers were assigned to profile PGO⁻ (low performance goals), being unconcerned about demonstrating their performance, and 38% of teachers were assigned to profile PGO⁺ (high performance goals). The smallest number of teachers (13%) was assigned to profile PAGO⁺ (high performance-avoidance goals), not wanting to demonstrate incompetence in front of others. Our findings also indicate that profile membership is not predicted by teachers' gender, age, or teaching experience.

Profile PGO⁻, characterized by average motivation and low performance goals, is consistent with the "intrinsic and confident" profile identified by Linnenbrink-Garcia et al. (2018) in their study on student motivation. The finding that the profiles differed on performance goals is in line with previous studies on goal orientation. PGO⁺ and PGO⁻ are similar to the profiles in Daumiller, Janke, Butler, Dickhäuser, & Dresel, 2020 and Kunst et al. (2018), showing interdependency among performance goals. From a critical point of view, one might argue that the absence of profile differences for the majority of the motivational characteristics in our sample does not indicate that LPA is more suitable than variable-centered analyses. However, the existence of profile PAGO⁺, clearly highlights the added value of a person-centered approach. In variable-centered studies, the typical high correlation between performance goals would imply a simultaneous occurrence of the two performance goals for the whole sample (Hulleman et al., 2010).

Profile PAGO⁺, however, indicates that performance goals do not need to be present at the same level but can be pursued independently. This profile configuration therefore extends the results of previous variable-centered studies by providing insight into an unexpected and divergent configuration of teachers' performance goals. This finding also highlights the importance of separating performance approach from avoidance strivings (Wormington & Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2017).

In light of these findings, the question arises as to why no significant profile differences were found for the majority of the motivational scales. Performance goals might have dominated the other four characteristics.⁶ Furthermore, considering the absolute level of the profile indicators (see Table 4), teachers in our sample seem, on average, highly motivated, which is reflected by high absolute mean values for enthusiasm, self-efficacy, learning goal orientation, and low means for work-avoidance goals. Based on the high means, one would conclude that teachers in our sample were indeed highly motivated and this consistency could explain the small profile differences for the majority of motivational characteristics. Teachers are generally considered to be a highly motivated sample, because most teachers are said to choose the profession for intrinsic reasons (Watt & Richardson, 2008). Interestingly, larger differences between profiles with respect to motivation have been shown for students (Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018). This might be due to the fact that student samples are more diverse and students are motivated to learn by a plethora of reasons. Our findings could therefore indicate that students and teachers experience motivation differently and that transferring findings from student motivation to teacher motivation might not always be possible.

The high motivation levels might, however, also be attributable to

⁶ To test this assumption, we conducted an additional latent profile analysis with teachers' enthusiasm, self-efficacy, and learning goals as indicators. Interestingly, the four-profile solution showed similar profile configurations, with no significant profile differences for self-efficacy and learning goals. Only enthusiasm showed small differences between the four profiles. These findings indicate that overrepresentation of goal orientations in the analyses of the present study does not seem to be the main reason for the lack of profound profile differences on the majority of the motivational scales; rather that ceiling effects in self-efficacy and learning goals might have influenced our results.

methodological biases such as self-selection or social desirability. Self-selection might have occurred, as participation in the study was voluntary and unmotivated teachers might have been underrepresented (Heckman, 2010). Moreover, a tendency to social desirability has been associated with self-reporting in general (Antin & Shaw, 2012) and with item formulation of learning goals specifically (Hulleman et al., 2010), as learning goals are often framed in a manner that makes it unlikely that respondents would reject the statement (e.g., “I aspire to improve my pedagogical knowledge and competence”). Although our study was anonymous, teachers may have filled out the questionnaire so as to appear in a good light – at least for items where the socially desirable responses were more transparent. In contrast, performance goal items (e.g., “I strive to prove to myself that I know more than others”) might be less transparent, thus resulting in a more heterogeneous response pattern.

4.2. Relations between motivational profiles and teaching quality and possible explanations

Although the link between teacher motivation and teaching quality is often assumed, we found no significant longitudinal relations between teachers’ motivational profiles and teaching quality. Classroom management, cognitive activation, and student support were not significantly predicted by profile membership, when controlling for teaching quality at Time 1. Since cross-sectional relations between profile membership and teaching quality as well as bivariate longitudinal relations were, with one exception,⁷ also statistically non-significant (see Fig. 2 and Table 1), the absence of longitudinal relations within the model is not very surprising. Also, profiles mainly differed with respect to performance goals. According to a study by Retelsdorf and Günther (2011), it may be that teachers’ goal orientations only indirectly influence teaching quality, for example mediated by teacher cognition (e.g., reference norms, when evaluating students).

Apart from the small profile differences, the results might also differ depending on how teaching quality is assessed. Previous studies have found that longitudinal relations between teacher motivation and teaching quality depend on the assessed perspective of teaching quality, where significant effects were often found when teachers report on their own teaching (e.g., Künsting et al., 2016). In research on teaching quality, the teacher’s perspective is usually assumed to be less valid and reliable than student or observer ratings (e.g., Clausen, 2002). As motivation is also assessed by teacher self-reporting, common method biases (see e.g., Williams et al., 2010) might be the reason for the relations identified in previous studies.

Finally, teaching quality included in a longitudinal manner, to control for stability, is suitable for a modifiable construct like teaching quality, which is influenced by several context factors (Bell et al., 2012). The fairly high stability of teaching quality across the examined time points might, however, have influenced our findings, leaving little variance to be explained through teacher motivation. This is especially true for classroom management (e.g., Praetorius et al., 2014). The non-significant associations between profile membership and teaching quality at Time 1, however, suggest similar results for a model without the control of Time 1.

Taken together, based on theoretical assumptions and empirical findings with respect to student motivation, this study adopted an integrative approach to teacher motivation. However, as profound profile differences were found for performance-goals only, and the profiles furthermore showed no significant associations with teaching quality, our findings do not seem to support the added value of the theoretical integration of EVT and AGT. Our results contrast with

previous research on student motivation (see Conley, 2012; Linnenbrink-Garcia et al., 2018), indicating that teacher and student motivation work differently. This is an important finding as theories about teacher motivation have often been employed from theories about student motivation (Kaplan, 2014). As our study is the first that integrates EVT and AGT in investigating the effect of teacher motivation on teaching quality in a person-centered approach, our findings need to be replicated in future studies to assess generalizability beyond the sample and instruments used. This is especially important as it is known that LPA results are quite dependent on the specifics of the samples and measurements used (Morin & Marsh, 2015). It might then be possible to identify meaningful effects of teacher motivation profiles on teaching quality, which could also have practical implications for teacher training.

4.3. Limitations and suggestions for future research

The first limitation of this study is that the motivational profiles were only estimated with respect to the first measurement point. Although this is suitable as a first step in identifying teachers’ motivational profiles, a longitudinal design would allow insight into the stability of such profiles. Furthermore, findings from experimental studies would provide important information regarding causal effects of profile membership on teaching quality, which is ultimately essential for the planning and implementation of teacher training or professional development.

Second, the reliability of the aggregated student assessment of teaching quality indicates low ICC values for cognitive activation at Time 1, with an increase at Time 2 (see Table 1). This finding is in line with other longitudinal studies focusing on other content-related aspects of teaching quality (e.g., clarity of instruction) at the beginning of secondary school (e.g., Fauth et al., 2020). In line with these authors, we hypothesize that the large within-classroom variation could be due to the transition to secondary school, as classes at Time 1 have just been reassembled and assigned to new teachers, possibly contributing to more divergent perceptions regarding cognitive activation compared to Time 2. This might be specifically the case for cognitive activation as it requires a higher level of inferences and is influenced by idiosyncratic interpretations to a larger degree, resulting in a lower level of agreement among students and lower temporal stability compared to classroom management and student support (e.g., Praetorius et al., 2014). The differences between the beginning of secondary school and the following school years seem to be further supported by previous findings regarding the associations between comparable teacher motivational characteristics and student-rated cognitive activation. Except for Butler and Shibaz (2014), the few studies addressing the relation between teacher motivation and student-rated cognitive activation reveal significant correlations in studies conducted at the end of secondary school (Grade 7–10 or above; Holzberger et al., 2013; Kunter et al., 2008), whereas the few existing studies conducted at the beginning of secondary school (Grade 5–6) also did not find significant correlations (see e.g., Lazarides et al., 2021).

Third, a critical reflection on the person-centered approach used in the present study should be addressed. As we were interested in the combination of numerous motivational characteristics, drawing on a profile analysis seemed worthwhile. However, our findings indicate that the person-centered approach did not allow for further information regarding the interplay of the examined motivational characteristics (with the exception of performance goals, outlined in section 4.1). Identifying qualitative profile differences represents a general challenge in research on LPA (Morin & Marsh, 2015), as often only level differences are found (e.g., Rodríguez et al., 2014). It should be noted, however, that quantitative profile differences can also be achieved with variable-centered analyses. To investigate the incremental explanatory value of the person-centered approach, a direct comparison with a variable-centered approach is needed (e.g., Daumiller, Janke, Butler, Dickhäuser, & Dresel, 2020). The absence of bivariate correlations of

⁷ There was a significant bivariate longitudinal relation between enthusiasm and classroom management as long as the stability of classroom management was not taken into account.

most teachers' motivational characteristics on teaching quality at Time 2 suggests that the results of a variable-centered approach would not, however, be substantially different.

Fourth, given the overrepresentation of goal orientation compared to enthusiasm and self-efficacy, it seems recommendable that future research assesses motivational constructs with a similar number of sub-dimensions. For this purpose, using the multidimensional measure of teachers' self-efficacy (Tschannen-Moran & Woolfolk Hoy, 2001) and the differentiation between enthusiasm for teaching and for the subject (see Kunter et al., 2011) seem suitable. Considering the multidimensional nature of teachers' intrinsic value orientations (e.g., interest, flow; see Kunter & Holzberger, 2014), it might be also helpful to include these into teachers' integrative profiles.

Fifth, the sample size per profile is partly low. Although a small sample size is generally not problematic for conducting LPA's as long as the profiles are well-separated (see Nylund-Gibson & Choi, 2018), the small sample size in profile PAGO⁺ might have led to a low statistical power. Our study should therefore be replicated with a larger sample.

Finally, a general problem of LPA is that there is no consensus regarding the labeling and interpretation of profiles. Some studies are based on absolute values, whereas others are based on z-standardization, with each having their advantages (see Wormington & Linnenbrink-Garcia, 2017). In this study, we chose standardized values to account for the different scaling of the motivational variables. One drawback of using z-scores is that information on absolute means is neglected. To combat this, we included information on the absolute mean levels in Table 4.

5. Conclusion

This study sheds light on the different motivational profiles of teachers by investigating a combination of multiple motivational characteristics. The three profiles identified suggest that teachers differ primarily in their goal orientation rather than in enthusiasm or self-efficacy. Contrary to theoretical assumptions and previous findings on student motivation, our study did not provide evidence for the added value of an integrative investigation on teacher motivation. However, since the identification of latent profiles strongly depends on the sample, our analyses should be replicated with different samples. Taken together, our findings do not provide conclusive information about how teacher motivation relates to teaching quality. However, by reporting null findings, we aim to contribute to a transparent reporting of empirical results and mitigate any publication bias or the file-drawer effect (Mehler et al., 2019).

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Declarations of interest

None.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Désirée Thommen: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – original draft. **Vanda Sieber:** Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Urs Grob:** Methodology, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. **Anna-Katharina Praetorius:** Conceptualization, Methodology, Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2021.101514>.

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